

Assessment and Comparison of Direct, Indirect and Total Bilirubin Levels Between Male and Female Diabetic and Non-Diabetic Patients in Sokoto State, North Western Nigeria

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Abstract

Bilirubin assessment have been shown by studies to be a useful biomarker in determining the cause of health conditions like jaundice, anaemia, and liver disease. Bilirubin is the final product of hemoglobin catabolism in the systemic circulation. This study examined and compare the serum direct, indirect and total bilirubin levels between male and female diabetic and non-diabetic patients in Sokoto State, Nigeria. A set of 40 diabetics and 20 non-diabetic patients (control), who attended Usman Danfodio University Teaching Hospital between January 2022 to January 2023 were used. The current study examined the subjects based on their age range of 20-30, 30-40 and 40-50 years age groups with a 4 and 15 patients who fell on 20-30 years age group for Non diabetic and Diabetic patients respectively, 7 and 12 patients fell on the 30-40 years age group for non diabetic and diabetic patients respectively and also, 9 and 13 number of patients fell on the 40-50 years age group for non-diabetic and diabetic patients respectively. The results revealed diabetic patients to have higher fasting blood glucose levels ($6.7 \pm 0.4 \text{ mmol/l}$) than the control ($5.2 \pm 0.6 \text{ mmol/l}$). Male diabetic patients had higher levels of direct bilirubin ($0.37 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg/dl}$) and indirect bilirubin ($0.31 \pm 0.03 \text{ mg/dl}$) compared to control with no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) for direct bilirubin level and significantly higher level of indirect bilirubin. They also had significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) levels of total bilirubin (1.53 ± 0.12) compared to the control (0.86 ± 0.08). Likewise, in female diabetic patients, direct bilirubin levels ($0.36 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg/dl}$) were higher than those of the control ($0.31 \pm 0.03 \text{ mg/dl}$) but the difference is not significant ($p > 0.05$). Female diabetic patient's indirect bilirubin levels ($0.92 \pm 0.11 \text{ mg/dl}$) were significantly higher than the control ($0.49 \pm 0.06 \text{ mg/dl}$). Moreover, female diabetic patient's total bilirubin levels ($1.28 \pm 0.11 \text{ mg/dl}$) were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the control ($0.80 \pm 0.08 \text{ mg/dl}$). This study observed a higher level of bilirubin in diabetic patients. Having high level of bilirubin in adult indicate several health conditions which involve gallstones, liver dysfunction, hepatitis, bile duct obstruction, intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy, and hemolytic anaemia. Therefore, bilirubin levels can be used as a biomarker of jaundice and liver diseases in the study area.

Keywords: Bilirubin, diabetes mellitus, direct bilirubin, fasting blood sugar, liver damage, total bilirubin

1.0 Introduction

Bilirubin is a red-orange compound that occurs in the normal catabolic pathway that breaks down heme in vertebrates. This catabolism is a necessary process in the body's clearance of waste products that arise from the destruction of

aged or abnormal red blood cells [1]. Bilirubin is created by the activity of biliverdin reductase on biliverdin, a green tetrapyrrolic bile pigment that is also a product of heme catabolism. Bilirubin, when oxidized, reverts to become biliverdin once again [2,3]. In 2020, Bryn et al. [5] found that bilirubin played a

beneficial role as a physiological antioxidant. Recent studies have shown that a mild increase in the bilirubin level within the physiological range has a protective effect against diabetes-related metabolic diseases [4]. The mechanism of the association between these metabolic diseases and bilirubin may be related to the insulin resistance status. Bilirubin could be involved in the signal transduction of the insulin signaling pathway, enhancing insulin sensitivity by reducing oxidative stress and inflammatory responses [5,6].

Total bilirubin (TBIL) is composed of about 80% indirect bilirubin (IBIL) and 20% direct bilirubin (DBIL). Through the hepatic enzyme UDP-glucuronyl transferase 1A1, IBIL is converted to DBIL [6]. These two kinds of bilirubin subtypes have different clinical implications. Some previous studies have reported the beneficial effects of moderate hyperbilirubinemia only involving TBIL or DBIL [7]. However, it has recently been reported that increasing IBIL is a promising therapeutic approach for treating metabolic diseases [8]. The relationships between serum bilirubins and diabetes-related impaired glucose metabolism are still controversial [9,10], which may be due to the different types of bilirubin. Indeed, few clinical studies have been conducted on the effects of bilirubin subtypes on insulin sensitivity [11,12].

High bilirubin levels in diabetes may be caused by the reduced HbA1c levels. HbA1c levels depend on the life-span of red cells in the circulation, and if the rate of turnover is higher than average, the HbA1c will be reduced, and the bilirubin increased, as bilirubin is formed from the breakdown of haemoglobin in red cells [13]. The Primary objective of the current study was to examine and compare the serum direct, indirect and total bilirubin levels between male and female diabetic and non-diabetic patients in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the study area

The study was conducted at Usman Danfodio University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto, Nigeria. Patients attending the hospital who have diabetes according to criteria of American Diabetics Association (A.D.A) were recruited [16]. Demographic information was collected.

Apparently healthy people, matched for age and gender, were recruited to serve as control. Blood samples were collected (5ml) for determination of bilirubin (conjugated and total) and fasting blood glucose levels.

2.2 Blood Collection

Blood samples were drawn from each volunteer patient using a 5 ml disposable plastic syringe. The blood was poured in a sample blank container and then centrifuged up to 5 minutes after it clotted. Serum was extracted and kept in the refrigerator till used. Bilirubin levels (direct and total) were measured using Clinical Chemistry Analyzer (WHY88000d Yunfeng ltd china).

2.3 Bilirubin Estimation Test

Using Jendrassic and Grof method [20], 100 μ l of sulphanyllic acid was added to both test and blank followed by a drop of nitrate to the test container. 500 μ l of Caffein was later added to both containers (test and blank containers) followed by 100 μ l of the sample. The mixture was incubated in the dark for 10 minutes at 25°C. After first incubation, the mixture was then treated with 100 μ l of the titrate to both containers (Test and Blank containers) and then incubated again for 5 minutes.

3.0 Result

3.1 Demographic data of the patients

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the patients. The age distribution indicates that the lowest age of the patients is 20 whereas, the highest falls on the 50 years of age comprising of 20 non-diabetic and 40 diabetic patients.

A total of forty patients of different sex (male and female) and equal number of 20 from each gender with age range of 20-30, 30-40 and 40-50 years, diagnosed with diabetes were analyzed.

There is significant difference between mean FBG of control (5.2 \pm 0.6) and diabetics on treatment (6.7 \pm 0.4). The number of diabetics was high than the control but % gender distribution is equal.

The control and diabetic subject have similar age range. Diabetic subject, even though on medication have significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher

fasting blood glucose levels compared to the control as seen in the table 3.1 below.

Table 1: Demographic and fasting blood glucose levels of the study subjects

Age range (years)	Non-Diabetic (control)	Diabetic subjects
20-30	4	15
30-40	7	12
40-50	9	13
Gender		
Males	10	20
Females	10	20
FBG(mmol/l)	5.2±0.6	6.7±0.4

Number in parentheses are percentage (FBS=Fasting blood glucose. mmol/l) = millimole per litre.

Bilirubin Levels of the study subject

Table 2 shows the bilirubin levels of the male and female diabetic and non-diabetic patients .The levels of both direct bilirubin , indirect and total bilirubin of diabetic male patients (0.37±0.02) were seen to be higher than in non-diabetic patients (0.31±0.03). Also, in female subjects the direct bilirubin (0.36±0.02), indirect bilirubin (0.92±0.11) and total bilirubin (1.28±0.11) levels in diabetic subjects are higher than in non-diabetic subjects with 0.31±0.03 level for direct bilirubin, 0.49±0.06 for indirect bilirubin and 0.80±0.08 level for total bilirubin. .

The direct bilirubin 0.37±0.02, indirect bilirubin 1.16±0.12 and total bilirubin levels 1.53±0.12 of male when compared to the female bilirubin levels 0.36±0.02, 0.92±0.11, 1.28±0.11 of both direct, indirect and total bilirubin respectively were seen to be higher as shown in table 2. below.

Table 2: Bilirubin Levels of the patients

Gender	Bilirubin levels	Non-diabetic (Control) (mg/dl)	Diabetic Subjects (mg/dl)
Male	Direct	0.31±0.03	0.37±0.02
	Indirect	0.55±0.07	1.16±0.12*
	Total	0.86±0.08	1.53±0.12*
Female	Direct	0.31±0.03	0.36±0.02
	Indirect	0.49±0.06	0.92±0.11*
	Total	0.80±0.08	1.28±0.11*

Values are expressed as Mean± SEM (n= 5). **P*<0.05: Significantly different from control. Oneway ANOVA followed by Dunnett Multiple Comparison Test
Bil= Bilirubin

There was a significantly (*P*<0.05) higher levels of indirect and total bilirubin in both male 1.16±0.12, 1.53±0.12 and female 0.92±0.11, 1.28±0.11diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic control subjects(male; indirect bilirubin 0.55±0.07 total bilirubin 0.86±0.08 Female; indirect bilirubin 0.49±0.06 total bilirubin 0.80±0.08) . In the current study, fasting blood glucose level and Bilirubin levels were significantly high in diabetic patients 6.7±0.4 1.53±0.12than in control group 5.2±0.6, 0.80±0.08 .

4.0 Discussion

The Primary objective of the current study was to examine and compare the serum direct, indirect and total bilirubin levels between male and female diabetic and nondiabetic patients in Sokoto State, Nigeria. We aimed to provide valuable information for effective management of bilirubin related health complication, as these factors have proven useful tools for the management of various diseases being an important biomarker in determining the cause of health conditions like jaundice, anaemia and liver disease.

In non-diabetic control group, there was no difference in the levels of direct bilirubin between

male 0.31 ± 0.03 and female subjects 0.31 ± 0.03 , whereas a higher levels of indirect and total bilirubin was observed in male 0.55 ± 0.07 , 0.86 ± 0.08 than in female control subjects 0.49 ± 0.06 , 0.80 ± 0.08 . These findings are in agreement with report of Leu et al. [14], who assessed the glucose and bilirubin levels in peoples with diabetes between the two genders and also albumin-to-creatinine ratio as a predictor of all-cause mortality and hospitalization of congestive heart failure in Chinese elder hypertensive patients with high cardiovascular risks.

The levels of direct, indirect and total bilirubin in male diabetic subject are higher than in female diabetic subjects. High levels of bilirubin in diabetic patients occurred due to low level of albumin which is responsible for transporting the unconjugated bilirubin into the liver for conjugation [20,21].

The result of the current study showed significantly high levels of serum total bilirubin in diabetic patients when compared to control. High Bilirubin level have protective activity due to its antioxidant action, anti-inflammatory effects on the vasculature, it is possible that an increase in serum total bilirubin level inhibits oxidative stress and inflammation processes [24]. These findings support the notion that people with high serum total bilirubin levels are protected against the development of micro vascular disease [25]. This finding is consistent with studies conducted by Byrne et al. [26] who worked on the Intensive blood pressure lowering in different age categories and cardiovascular diseases. This can be due to high bilirubin which may inhibit the glycation of hemoglobin by reducing oxidative stress [17]. Sugars react non-enzymatically with a wide range of proteins to form early glycation products and oxidative stress is involved in the glycation reaction[27]. Oxidative stress can facilitate the autoxidation of glucose to dicarbonyl intermediate although the differences were statistically significant [28]. The means of direct, in direct and total bilirubin were higher than the control values

5.0 Conclusion

Diabetic patients were observed to have high bilirubin levels influenced by glucose metabolic derangement. There is a gender disparity in the levels of indirect and total bilirubin between male

and female patients where male diabetic patients were observed to have high indirect and total bilirubin levels.

6.0 References

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